

Organic Acids as Analytical Reagent. Part 1 : Estimation of Zirconium by Gallic Acid

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Gallic acid has been found to be a selective reagent for the estimation of zirconium. The acid gives white crystalline precipitate at pH of 4.8. The precipitate is ignited and weighed as ZrO_2 . Cations like Ca^{+2} , Ba^{+2} , Sr^{+2} , Mn^{+2} , Co^{+2} , Ni^{+2} , Fe^{+3} do not interfere in the estimation,

ORGANIC acids have been investigated by several workers for the estimation of Thorium¹⁻³ and Zirconium⁹⁻¹². The authors have systematically investigated gallic acid for the estimation of zirconium. The reagent gives curdy white, insoluble and easily washable ppt at pH 4.8 (maintained by acetic acid, sodium acetate buffer).

Metal ions like Ca^{+2} , Ba^{+2} , Sr^{+2} , Mn^{+2} , Co^{+2} , Ni^{+2} , Fe^{+3} are found not to interfere at pH 4.8. Their separation from zirconium is possible by single precipitation.

Experimental

Reagent solution: A 2% solution of potassium salt of gallic acid was prepared by dissolving the requisite amount of acid (BDH) in calculated amount of KOH in hot distilled water.

Standard Zirconium solution: Stock solution of zirconium was prepared from the requisite amount of $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ in distilled water. Metal content of the solution was determined gravimetrically¹³.

Solution of other cations: Metal chlorides and nitrates (BDH/AR) were dissolved in distilled water and analysed by standard methods.

Analytical Procedure

Varying amounts of the solution, (containing 0.1170 to 0.0026 g ZrO_2) were heated to boiling. The pH of solutions was adjusted at 4.8 and the boiling solution of 2% potassium salt of gallic acid was slowly added with constant stirring till complete precipitation. The ppt was digested on a water bath for 30 min. and was filtered and washed with 1% hot reagent solution and finally with hot water. The filter paper with the precipitate was dried, ignited and weighed as ZrO_2 . Even .0026 g of ZrO_2 gives enough ppt for easy handling (Table 1).

Effect of pH: The effect of pH was studied in the range from 4.1 to 5.23. At pH 4.1 and below no precipitation occurs at all but as the pH is raised the

precipitate formation begins. The correct results are obtained at 4.8 pH but as the pH is raised, the precipitating reagent itself starts precipitating resulting in higher results (Table 2).

TABLE 1—GRAVIMETRIC ESTIMATION OF VARYING AMOUNTS OF ZIRCONIUM USING GALLIC ACID

Experiment No.	pH of the Solution = 4.80		
	ZrO_2 taken in g	ZrO_2 found in g	Error in g
1	.1170	.1172	+ .0002
2	.0708	.0708	± .0000
3	.0088	.0090	+ .0002
4	.0048	.0047	- .0001
5	.0026	.0026	± .0000

TABLE 2—ESTIMATION OF ZIRCONIUM AT DIFFERENT pH

Experiment No.	ZrO_2 taken = .0512 g		
	pH of solution	ZrO_2 found in g	Error in g
1	4.05	No ppt	—
2	4.63	.0506	- .0006
3	4.80	.0512	± .0000
4	4.99	.0520	+ .0008
5	5.23	.0524	+ .0012

Separation from foreign ions: A number of cations such as Ca^{+2} , Ba^{+2} , Sr^{+2} , Mn^{+2} , Co^{+2} , Ni^{+2} and Fe^{+3} do not give ppt under these conditions. (Table 3).

TABLE 3—ESTIMATION OF ZIRCONIUM IN PRESENCE OF FOREIGN IONS

pH of the Solution = 4.80 ZrO₂ taken = .0512 g

Metal Ions		ZrO ₂ found in g	Error in g
Added	in g		
Ca ⁺²	0.2900	.0512	± .0000
Ba ⁺²	0.2900	.0514	+ .0002
Sr ⁺²	0.1408	.0512	± .0000
Mn ⁺²	0.2402	.0514	+ .0002
Co ⁺²	0.2854	.0510	- .0002
Ni ⁺²	0.3562	.0512	± .0000
Fe ⁺³	0.2742	.0510	- .0002

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